

Physical non-linearity of unidirectional polymer matrix composites in cyclic fatigue life analysis

M. Magin and N. Himmel

Institut für Verbundwerkstoffe GmbH – University Kaiserslautern
Erwin-Schrödinger-Str. Geb. 58 – 67663 Kaiserslautern, Germany
norbert.himmel@ivw.uni-kl.de

SUMMARY

The efficient use of fiber reinforced polymer matrix composites in load-carrying structures requires detailed analyses to assess their mechanical performance, cost, and weight saving aspects. To accurately analyze the cyclic fatigue life of composite laminates, the influence of the physical non-linearity of the unidirectional lamina in the cyclic fatigue life analysis was examined using enhanced material models.

Keywords: fiber reinforced polymer matrix composites, cyclic fatigue, fatigue life analysis, physical non-linearity

Introduction

Fiber reinforced composites are widely used in aerospace and mechanical engineering due to their advantageous stiffness and strength to weight ratio and fatigue resistance. To assess the cyclic fatigue life of fiber reinforced polymers in numerical simulations the underlying material models need to consider the physical non-linearity of static as well as cyclic material parameters, e.g. stress-strain and S-N curves. In this work the experimental characterization of the material non-linearities of three epoxy resin composites with glass and carbon fiber reinforcement typical for applications in the aircraft and wind energy industries as well as the implementation of the derived material models into a fatigue life prediction algorithm are presented.

Experiments

Material characteristics were determined experimentally for three different fiber reinforced plastics with the material data base being extended continuously. The most extensive characterization was carried out for a $[0]_8$, $[\pm 45]_{3S}$ and $[-45/0/-45/90]_S$ CFRP. A 2-component vinylester-urethane hybrid resin (DSM) toughened by liquid, epoxy-terminated butadiene-nitrile rubber (10 weight-%, Hycar ETBN, Hanse Chemie) was used for the impregnation of a unidirectional (UD) carbon fiber woven fabric (style 796, HTA 5131, 400 tex, stabilized by 34 tex E-glass EC 9 1383 in the weft direction, 270 g/m², E.C.C.) in a closed mold resin infusion process at +80 °C, cured at +150 °C for 40 minutes and post-cured at +200 °C for 2 hours. In this article this material is denoted as CF/VEUH:ETBN. Further information of this composite system is available in [1].

Furthermore, static and tension-tension cyclic fatigue tests were completed for a unidirectional GFRP. As glass fiber material a uni-directional E-glass non-crimp fabric

made by Saertex (area mass of 957 g/m^2 , stabilization by approximately 10 % PES thread) was used. The specimens were impregnated in a vacuum assisted resin infusion process using the Huntsman two-component epoxy resin system Araldite LY 1564 SP with hardener Aradur 3487 in a mass ratio of 100:34. After resin infusion at $+40 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, the laminate was heated to $+60 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 120 minutes for curing. The cured plates were tempered in a convection oven at $+80 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 8 hours. The specimens were produced with the lay-ups $[\pm 45]_{2s}$, $[0]_4$, and $[90]_4$. This material is denoted as GF-EP.

Finally, $[\pm 45]_{8s}$, $[0]_8$, and $[90]_{16}$ CFRP specimens denoted as CF-EP were prepared using a uni-directional non-crimp fabric by Hexcel with AS7 J 12K carbon fibers and a polyester thread transverse to the fiber direction at a distance of 50 mm. The used matrix material was Hexcel RTM-6. The resin was injected at $+120^\circ\text{C}$ followed by hardening at $+160^\circ\text{C}$ for 2 hours and curing at $+180^\circ\text{C}$ for 2 hours.

The experimental characterizations of the composite materials presented above included quasi-static tests of unidirectional specimens from the virgin composites and specimens with previous cyclic fatigue loading. Furthermore, S-N-curves, residual strength and stiffness degradation were determined experimentally.

Fig. 1 shows the non-linear σ_1 - ε_1 curves of $[0]_8$ CF-EP in uni-axial tension. Strains were measured using contact-free laser and video extensometers during the tests. The fiber parallel stress-strain characteristic for CF-EP was found to be progressive because of the stiffness increase of the carbon fibers which is believed to result from a re-alignment of the crystalline graphite planes during uni-axial loading [2].

Fig. 1: Non-linear quasi-static σ_1 - ε_1 curves of $[0]_8$ CF-EP in uniaxial tension.

Fig. 2 shows the non-linear τ_{21} - γ_{21} curves of $[\pm 45/-45]_{8s}$ CF-EP in uni-axial tension. Strains were measured using contact-free laser and video extensometers during the tests. As to be expected, the shear stress- shear strain characteristic for CF-EP was found to be strongly degressive.

Fig. 2: Non-linear quasi-static τ_{21} - γ_{21} curves of $[+45/-45]_{8S}$ CF-EP in uniaxial tension.

Fig. 3 shows the experimentally determined fatigue life for the GF-EP material, tested transverse to the fiber direction at a stress ratio of $R = +0.1$ with constant amplitude sinusoidal load under load control, a frequency $f = 5$ Hz under ambient laboratory conditions. Two linear and one non-linear S-N curves are drawn in Fig. 3, showing that the linear models would, if extended to the range of lower fatigue lives N , overestimate the static strength, whereas the non-linear model could be curve-fitted to represent the experimentally determined quasi-static strength, hence allowing a more realistic approximation of low cycle fatigue.

Fig. 3: S-N curves of $[90]_4$ GF-EP after constant amplitude cyclic loading ($R = +0.1$, upper stress amplitude $S_0 = 30$ to 60 MPa, $f = 5$ Hz, load control, ambient conditions).

Strength degradation tests were carried out on 0° specimens after pre-loading the specimens by constant amplitude cyclic fatigue (upper stress amplitude $S_o = 1,100$ MPa, stress ratio of $R = +0.1$, sinusoidal load under load control with a frequency $f = 5$ Hz at ambient laboratory conditions). At 10^3 , 10^4 , 10^5 and $7 \cdot 10^5$ cycles, the fatigue testing was stopped, and the corresponding specimens were tested to failure under quasi-static tensile loading. During quasi-static testing the specimen strains parallel and perpendicular to the loading direction were measured using contact-free laser and video extensometers. The strength degradation curve applying eq. (7) as proposed by Hahn and Kim [3] is presented in this figure.

Fig. 4: Strength degradation of $[0]_8$ CF/ETBN-VEUH laminate after cyclic loading ($R = +0.1$, upper stress amplitude $S_o = 1,100$ MPa, $n = 10^3, 10^4, 10^5, 7 \cdot 10^5$) and Hahn-Kim model [3], eq. (7).

To determine the stiffness degradation after cyclic preloading the Young's modulus was measured fiber parallel at strains 0.05 and 0.25 % during a quasi-static tensile test. In addition the dynamic modulus which is the quotient of the stress and strain differences at the upper and lower reversal point of the hysteresis loop was continuously determined during the fatigue experiments. Fig. 5 shows exemplarily the stiffness reduction of the fiber parallel modulus of the GF-EP after cyclic pre-loading to 50,000, 400,000 and 800,000 cycles and the modeling according to Ogin [4], eq. (6).

Fig. 5: Young's modulus of $[0]_4$ GF-EP after cyclic preloading.

Numerical analyses

Methodology

The most comprehensive method for fatigue life analysis today is the Critical Element Concept developed by Reifsnider and Stinchcomb ([5]–[7]). This methodology chooses a structural volume which is representative for the overall structure, loading, fatigue damage and failure process of the laminate. This representative volume is subdivided in a critical and a sub-critical element. The latter represents sub-critical damage processes leading to stiffness degradation and stress transfer, but not to the total failure of the laminate. The critical element is a volume within a composite laminate the failure of which results in the complete failure of the laminate.

A computer program developed at IVW is based on the Critical Element Concept and incorporates different models of linear and non-linear material behavior, S-N curves, stiffness and strength degradation models as well as Puck's inter-fiber failure (IFF) criterion.

To describe non-linear material stress-strain relationships, different mathematical models were investigated, i.e. exponential, bi-linear and a modified Ramberg-Osgood model ([8], [9]), eq. (1). The latter was chosen since it yields a good description of the material behavior.

$$\varepsilon_{ij}(\sigma_{ij}) = \frac{\sigma_{ij}}{E_{ij,0}} + \xi_p \left(\frac{\sigma_{ij}}{\sigma_p} \right)^e \quad (1)$$

In eq. (1) $E_{ij,0}$ and σ_p denote the elastic modulus and the maximum tensile stress at failure of the laminate, σ_{ij} is the stress component acting in the j direction on a plane with the normal vector i . The shape parameters ξ_p and e were determined from the measured stress-strain curve data applying the least squares method.

S-N curves for uni-directional laminates under cyclic loading parallel to the fiber direction are described using a non-linear function in $\log(N)$, with N representing the fatigue life of the material.

$$S_o(N) = \frac{R_{11}^t}{1 + \left(\frac{A \cdot \log(N)^B}{R_{11}^t} \right)^C} \quad (2)$$

In contrast to the linear form, which is commonly used, the non-linear form prevents the calculation of fatigue lives for stress levels S_o higher than the quasi-static strength R_{11}^t of the material. A , B and C in this equation are free parameters.

Stiffness degradation occurs on two stages in the computation algorithm: a quasi-static failure analysis computes the stiffness reduction due to the sub-critical IFF and a fatigue life analysis the degradation of stiffness due to fatigue.

The stiffness of a uni-directional ply is reduced by multiplying certain elements $[Q_{ij}]$ of the stiffness matrix with a corresponding degradation parameter η ($0 \leq \eta \leq 1$). One of the simplest methods to determine η is the stiffness reduction model of Chiu [8] (Fig. 6 b). This model postulates a complete degradation of the elastic modulus down to its residual value as soon as the first sub-critical failure (inter-fiber cracking) occurs, i.e. the IFF stress exposure f_{IFF} exceeds 1. Advantages of the Chiu model are the straightforward implementation into computing algorithms and the fact that it leads to conservative life cycle estimations. On the other hand, it allows no parameter variation due to its binary character. In contrast, the degradation model of Puck (Fig. 6 a) includes a continuous decrease of the degradation factors η_E and η_G (the index E representing factor for the Young's modulus, G for the shear modulus):

$$\eta_{E,G} = \frac{1 - \eta_R}{1 + c(f_{\text{IFF}} - 1)^\xi} + \eta_R \quad (3)$$

In this model c and ξ are free parameters. The degradation factors start at 1 followed by a steep decrease and converge gradually to their residual values, e.g. to $\eta_{E,R} = 0.03$ and $\eta_{G,R} = 0.65$ for CFRP. Chiu's model may be seen as a special case of the Puck model leading instantaneously to full degradation at the occurrence of IFF.

Fig. 6: a) Degradation factors η_E and η_G for CFRP according to the stiffness degradation model of Puck [2], b) Stiffness degradation model of Chiu [8]

Comparisons of fatigue experiments on CF/VEUH:ETBN composites and analytical predictions showed that delamination occurring in the material can not be modeled with the basic form of the CLT, hence requiring a modification to account for delamination effects. This modification was included in the calculation of the stiffness matrix $[Q]$ for the laminate, eq. (4). E_1 , E_2 and G_{21} are determined by analyzing stresses based on the corresponding non-linear stress-strain curves, the Poisson's ratio is assumed to be constant. The stiffness degradation due to IFF is considered by d_{deg} ($0.03 \leq d_{deg} \leq 1$) while delamination effects are modeled by a delamination factor $d_{del}(S_{x,o}, n)$. As presented in [1] this approach is in good agreement with the stiffness degradation determined in the experiment.

$$[Q] = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{d_{del}(\sigma_x, n) \cdot E_1(\sigma_1, n)}{1 - \nu_{12}^* \cdot \nu_{21}} & d_{deg, E_2} \cdot \frac{\nu_{\perp\parallel} \cdot E_2(\sigma_2, n)}{1 - \nu_{12}^* \cdot \nu_{21}} & 0 \\ \nu_{12}^* \cdot \frac{d_{del}(\sigma_x, n) \cdot E_1(\sigma_1, n)}{1 - \nu_{12}^* \cdot \nu_{21}} & d_{deg, E_2} \cdot \frac{E_2(\sigma_2, n)}{1 - \nu_{12}^* \cdot \nu_{21}} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & d_{deg, G_{21}} \cdot G_{21}(\tau_{21}, n) \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

$$\nu_{12}^* = d_{deg, E_2} \cdot \frac{\nu_{21} \cdot E_2(\sigma_2, n)}{d_{del}(\sigma_x, n) \cdot E_1(\sigma_1, n)} \quad (5)$$

d_{del} can be represented by a hyperbolic sine function, depending on the maximum stress $S_{x,o}$ as described in [1].

Fatigue induced stiffness degradation can be described as a function of fatigue cycles n by

$$\frac{E_x(n)}{E_{x,0}} = 1 - \left(\frac{S_{x,o}}{E_{x,0}} \right) \cdot \log(n)^2 + \left(\frac{S_{x,o}}{E_{x,0}} \right)^\alpha \cdot n^2 \text{ with } \alpha(S_{x,o}) = a - b \cdot \left(\frac{S_{x,o}}{E_{x,0}} \right) \quad (6)$$

The original form of this equation was proposed by Ogin [4] and extended by the term $\left(\frac{S_{x,0}}{E_{x,0}}\right)^\alpha \cdot n^2$ to account for the stiffness decrease starting at rather low cycle numbers.

$S_{x,0}$ represents the maximum stress amplitude, $E_{x,0}$ the Young's modulus measured in the first ascending part of the stress-strain curve of the first cycle. The free parameters of the exponent α as defined in equation (6) were determined from experimental data applying the least squares method.

The strength degradation model

$$F_R(n, S_o) = R_{11}^t - (R_{11}^t - S_o) \left(\frac{n}{N}\right)^k, \quad (7)$$

developed by Hahn and Kim [3] includes an intrinsic stress-based fatigue failure criterion as, for a given stress amplitude S_o , failure is predicted at that cycle number n , if the instantaneous stress in the critical element is equal or higher than the remaining strength F_R of the material. This model takes the loading history as well as the quasi-static strength R_{11}^t and the fatigue life N into account. In this model k is a free parameter.

Fig. 7 shows a flow-chart of the computer program consisting of two main parts: the quasi-static failure analysis and the fatigue life prediction. In the first part, a ply-by-ply static failure analysis is performed for each loading step i . This analysis consists of a non-linear stress-strain analysis based on the classical laminated plate theory, the evaluation of the stress exposure of the laminate according to the IFF criterion of Puck and a stiffness degradation model taking into account the corresponding sub-critical IFF modes [10]. In case of IFF modes A or B, which represent combined in-plane transverse tensile or compression and shear stresses, the stiffness degradation is modeled according to Puck's model, and the stress analysis is re-iterated with reduced stiffness parameters. IFF mode C, representing high transverse compressive and shear stresses, has to be regarded as critical with respect to the integrity of the laminate, as this mode is supposed to cause wedge shaped fracture fragments which may destroy adjacent plies. Consequently, in the occurrence of mode C IFF, the algorithm assumes total failure and the end of the fatigue life of the laminate.

If no further IFF is predicted the resulting stress state will be transferred to the second part of the program. In this part the stiffness and strength are evaluated, which requires a re-calculation of the stress state in the critical element. Finally, the failure criterion for fatigue $F_R(n) \geq \sigma_1(n)$ which is defined as a modified maximum stress criterion, relates the instantaneous stress $\sigma_1(n)$ in the fiber-parallel direction to the instantaneous residual strength $F_R(n)$ of the critical element. If $F_R(n) > \sigma_1(n)$ no fatigue failure is predicted which initiates the calculation of the next loading step $i+1$. $F_R(n) \leq \sigma_1(n)$ indicates failure of the critical element which, in turn, defines the end of the fatigue life of the analyzed laminate.

Fig. 7: Fatigue life prediction methodology [1]

Non-linear stress analysis

The non-linear stress analysis uses a secant modulus iteration method to determine the strain associated with the stress in a given load step. The iteration starts with the tangent modulus $E_{ij,0}$ in the origin of the stress-strain curve and iterates within k sub-steps to the final point on the non-linear stress-strain curve and the corresponding secant modulus $E_{ij}(n=i)$ for this load-step (Fig. 8, left). By using the sub-steps, the algorithm can detect IFF at stress levels lower than $\sigma_{ij}(n=i)$. In addition, the algorithm becomes numerically stable for stress-strain curves with pronounced curvatures. The iteration of load step $i+1$ starts with the secant modulus determined in step i (Fig. 8, right). For $\sigma_{ij}(n=i) \leq \sigma_{ij}(i)$ the stress analysis is linear. For $\sigma_{ij}(i+1) > \sigma_{ij}(i)$ the stress analysis is linear for l sub-steps while a new secant modulus $E_{ij}(i+1)$ is iterated in the last m sub-steps ($l+m=k$).

Fig. 8: Secant modulus iteration for non-linear stress analysis

Influence of non-linear stress-strain curve on fatigue life prediction

A parameter study, presented in [11], showed that the influence of the fiber-parallel stress-strain relationship $\xi_p(\sigma_{11}-\epsilon_{11})$, eq. (1), is particularly strong as it influences directly the stress transfer to the 0° plies and, hence, the stress amplitude S_o in the critical element. An example of a non-linear fiber parallel stress-strain behavior for CF-EP is shown in Fig. 1.

The normal transverse stress-strain behavior of the GF-EP composite was found to be non-linear due to the presence of a less brittle matrix in combination with the influence of the transverse PES stabilizer thread allowing load transfer in the matrix beyond IFF.

The combination of both material non-linearities showed a rather strong influence on the fatigue life, therefore the conclusion could be drawn to include the non-linear fiber parallel and transverse stress-strain relationships in the algorithms to predict the fatigue life more realistically.

Variable amplitude loading in non-linear fatigue life prediction

Quasi-isotropic CF/VEUH:ETBN laminates were tested under miniTWIST variable amplitude loadings with different stress levels and compared to the fatigue life prediction using the non-linear parameters listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Material parameters for CF/VEUH-ETBN (cf. [1])

Equation	Material	Parameter	Value
Mod. Ramberg-Osgood, eq. (1)	CF/VEUH-ETBN [0] ₈	$E_{1,0}$	122,991 MPa
		ξ_p	-0.000564
		σ_p	1,540 MPa
		e	2.4
	CF/VEUH-ETBN [+45/-45] _{3S}	$G_{21,0}$	4,318 MPa
		ξ_p	-0.012
		τ_p	62 MPa
		e	3.44
Non-linear S-N curve, eq. (2)	CF/VEUH-ETBN [0] ₈	R_{11}^t	1540 MPa
		A	490 MPa
		B	0.533
		C	4.8
Stiffness degradation, eq. (3)	CF/VEUH-ETBN [+45/0/-45/90] _s	$\eta_E = \text{const.}$	0.03
		$\eta_G = \text{const.}$	0.67
Fatigue induced stiffness degradation, eq. (6)		a	8.51
		b	680
Strength degradation, eq. (7)		k	2.6

The experimental results [1] are indicated as black rectangles in Fig. 9. In addition, this figure shows the results of fatigue life predictions considering linear and non-linear stress-strain curves. To compare the influence of stiffness degradation compared to a fully degraded laminate, in which only the 0° plies remained to transfer load, different fatigue life predictions including linear and non-linear stress-strain curves were analyzed. The quasi-isotropic laminate was analyzed assuming linear stress-strain curves without considering any stiffness degradation, while in another analysis only the 0° plies of the laminate were considered. Furthermore, the fatigue life was predicted for linear and non-linear stress-strain curves combined with stiffness degradation in off-axis plies due to IFF and delaminations. The comparison of experimental and simulation results shows that the assumption of linear stress-strain behavior combined with the neglecting of stiffness degradation overestimates the fatigue life, while it is underestimated by the analytical reduction of the multidirectional laminate to its 0° plies. The predictions based on linear material behavior combined with stiffness reduction due to IFF and delaminations approximate the test results, while the best correlations are obtained for non-linear stress-strain modeling combined with IFF and delamination induced stiffness reduction.

Fig. 9: Test results and fatigue life predictions for $[+45/0/-45/90]_s$ CF/VEUH:ETBN under miniTWIST variable amplitude loading [1]

Concluding remarks

The presented fatigue life simulation methodology uses advanced material models to take non-linearity into account, e.g. non-linear stress-strain and S-N curves. Also strength and delamination induced stiffness degradation are incorporated in the algorithm. Although the usage of non-linear material properties means substantially increased experimental and numerical effort, it can be stated that more simplified models are less suited for fatigue life prediction. Therefore, to achieve a more realistic estimation of the material behavior, material non-linearity as well as non-linear S-N curves and delamination effects should be taken into account.

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